

Kinetics of the adsorption of glucose at the alumina-solution interface

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Manuscript received 15 July 1999, revised 4 November 1999, accepted 26 November 1999

The adsorption kinetics of glucose at the alumina-solution interface have been studied colorimetrically at pH 6.8 and room temperature (25°). Various kinetic and thermodynamic parameters of the adsorption process have been evaluated. The effects of variation in experimental conditions of the system are studied.

Carbohydrates in aqueous solution has been a subject of study over a long period of time¹. In several situations the interaction between a solid and carbohydrate molecules in aqueous suspensions become important as this commonly leads to removal of carbohydrate molecules from solution leading to industrial applications². For example, the recovery and concentration from dilute sugar solutions improves the prospects of using dilute sugar streams for fermentation purposes³. The present contribution aims at studying the statics and kinetics of the adsorption of glucose from its aqueous solution onto the alumina with an object to explore optimum conditions for separation of glucose by chromatographic methods.

Results and Discussion

Concentration effect : On increasing the concentration of glucose in the range 0.1–0.7 mg/ml, the adsorption increases and finally levels off as shown in Fig. 1. We also continued the shaking period upto 4 h and observed no desorption of glucose.

Fig. 1. Plot of amounts of glucose adsorbed vs the equilibrium concentrations.

Adsorption isotherm : The adsorption isotherm (Fig. 1) resembles a typical Langmuirian plot and indicates that the adsorption process follows the Langmuir isotherm equation⁴,

$$\frac{C_e}{a} = \frac{1}{a_s b} + \frac{C_e}{a_s} \quad (1)$$

where, $b = k_1/k_2$, k_1 and k_2 are the rate constants for adsorption and desorption, respectively, and a and a_s the amount adsorbed per gram of the adsorbent at equilibrium concentration (C_e) and at saturation, respectively. From the slope and intercept of the linear plot drawn, between C_e/a and C_e (eq. 1), the value of b has been calculated to be 5.50 ml mg⁻¹. The graphical value of a_s (adsorption capacity) is identical to the experimental value (Table 1).

Table 1. Adsorption and kinetic parameters for the adsorption of glucose onto alumina

Adsorption coefficient (b) ml mg ⁻¹	Adsorption capacity (experimental) mg g ⁻¹	Adsorption capacity (graphical) mg g ⁻¹	Rate constants × 10 ⁵	
			Adsorption (k ₁) ml mg ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	Desorption (k ₂) s ⁻¹
8.40	20.0	21.1	9.2	0.011

Kinetics of adsorption has been studied by monitoring progress of the adsorption process at different time intervals and the rate of adsorption was found almost constant upto nearly 75 min and then it gradually decreased, attaining a constant value finally.

The rate constants k_1 and k_2 for the adsorption and desorption, respectively, follow the scheme as described elsewhere in detail⁵.

Kinetic scheme : According to Langmuir's adsorption isotherm equation, the rate of adsorption (R_{ad}) is given by

$$R_{ad} = k_1 C(1 - \theta) - k_2 \theta \quad (2)$$

where, k_1 , k_2 , C and θ have their usual significance. Now, in order to calculate the rate constant for adsorption (k_1),

the following assumptions can be adopted : (i) The rate of adsorption may be approximated as equal to the rate of decrease in concentration of the adsorbate solution, i.e.

$$R_{ad} = -\frac{dC}{dt} \quad (3)$$

(ii) In the initial (and obviously linear) portion of the adsorbed amount versus time curve, the rate of desorption may be neglected as the adsorption is much dominating in the initial time periods, i.e. $k_2 \ll k_1$, and as a consequence the second term of the right-hand-side of eq. (2) can be ignored in comparison to the first term, i.e.

$$k_1 C(1 - \theta) \gg k_2 \theta$$

(iii) The surface coverage (θ) may be approximated as

$$\theta = \frac{q(t)}{q_{eq}} = \frac{C_0 - C}{C_0 - C_e} \quad (4)$$

where, $q(t)$ and q_{eq} are the amount adsorbed at time t and at equilibrium and C_0 is the initial bulk concentration of adsorbate solution. Thus, following the above simplification, we can write eq. (2) as

$$-\frac{dC}{dt} = k_1 C \frac{C - C_e}{C_0 - C_e} \quad (5)$$

If equilibrium adsorption arrives at much latter stage, then numerical value of C_e may be ignored in comparison to C_0 and C (as an approximation), and eq. (5) reduces to

$$-\frac{dC}{C^2} = k_1 \frac{dt}{C_0} \quad (6)$$

Upon complete integration of eq. (6), we get

$$-\frac{1}{C} = k_1 \frac{t}{C_0} + \frac{1}{C_0} \quad (7)$$

Obviously from the plot between $1/C$ and t , the value of k_1 may be calculated. Once k_1 is known, the value of k_2 may be known since k_1/k_2 has already been calculated. The values of k_1 and k_2 for a fixed concentration of glucose solution are summarized in Table 1.

Mode of adsorption : Since the point of zero charge (PZC) of the alumina used in the present investigation is 9.0 and the experimental pH is 6.8, the alumina must have both AlOH and AlOH_2^+ type of groups on its surface. Now, considering the ring structure of glucose, different types of interactions between the glucose molecule and alumina surface may be postulated. The hydroxyls of the carbons of different glucose structures interact with the aluminols ($-\text{AlOH}$) and protonated aluminols ($-\text{AlOH}_2^+$) of the alumina surface via electrostatic and H-bonding forces and, consequently, the adsorption will be purely physical in nature irrespective of the pyranose or furanose ring-structure of the glucose molecule.

pH effect : The pH of the suspension has been varied in the range 3–11.7 by the appropriate additions of HCl/NaOH . The results indicate that the amount of ad-

sorbed glucose increases with increasing pH of the suspension and attains a maximum adsorption at pH 8.8 and thereafter starts decreasing. The causes for the observed behaviour may be given as follows. (i) At pH 3.0, the alumina surface acquires a net positive charge due to AlOH_2^+ groups and the glucose molecules are held to the surface. After increasing pH of the suspension the number of protonated aluminols (AlOH_2^+) decreases resulting in a decrease of electrostatic repulsion between the $-\text{O}^{\delta-}\text{H}^{\delta+}$ of glucose molecule and AlOH_2^+ group of the alumina. This decreasing repulsion results in an increasing adsorption of glucose with increasing pH of the suspension. This increase continues till the pH becomes 8.8 which is almost identical to the point of zero charge of alumina. At this pH, the surface becomes electrically neutral and the adsorption reaches maximum. On further increasing the pH beyond 8.8, the alumina surface acquires increasing negative charge due to increasing number of AlO^- groups on its surface and at this moment, the repulsive forces begin to operate between the AlO^- groups of alumina and $-\text{O}^{\delta-}\text{H}^{\delta+}$ of glucose molecule. Thus, with further increase in the pH, the adsorption decreases. (ii) Another reason for the observed decrease in adsorption of glucose in alkaline pH range is that at higher pH the glucose undergoes isomerization reaction⁶ and converts into fructose. We have carried out adsorption of fructose onto alumina under identical experimental conditions and found it to be 4.6 mg g^{-1} which is less than half the value obtained for the adsorbed glucose (11.6 mg g^{-1}). Thus, due to the conversion of glucose into fructose in the higher pH range the adsorption decreases.

Salt effect : The effect of addition of various anions and cations in the concentration range 0.01–0.08 M to the alumina suspension have been observed on the adsorption of glucose. The results reveal that in the case of anionic addition, the adsorption increases in the following increasing order, $\text{Cl}^- < \text{SO}_4^{2-} < \text{PO}_4^{3-}$, while in case of cations, the adsorption remains almost unaffected. The possible explanations may be that in the case of addition of anions, the electrostatic repulsions between the AlOH_2^+ and AlOH groups of alumina surface and $-\text{OH}^{\delta+}$ of glucose molecules are screened by the added anions and, therefore, the adsorption increases. It is also clear that the adsorption increases with increasing charge of the added anions and thus the observed order of effectiveness of anions is also justified. Also, when cations such as Na^+ , Ca^{2+} , Al^{3+} are added to the alumina suspension, the adsorption remains almost unaffected. The reason for such a behaviour is that the added cation increases the existing electrostatic repulsion between the AlOH_2^+ and AlOH of alumina and $-\text{O}-\text{H}$ of glucose molecules, while the same cations also increase

the electrostatic attraction between the AlOH_2^+ and AlOH of alumina and $-\text{O}-\text{H}$ of glucose molecules. Thus, both the opposing factors ultimately counterbalance each other and the adsorption remains unaffected.

Temperature effect : The effect of increase in temperature on the adsorption of glucose has been studied by carrying out in the temperature range of $5-45^\circ$. The results show that with rise in temperature, the adsorption decreases. The greater amount of adsorption at lower temperature may be due to strengthening of intermolecular forces and possible agglomeration of glucose molecules (as in case of dyes also⁷). Also, at higher temperature, the escaping tendency of glucose molecules from the solid to the bulk phase⁸ may also result in a lower adsorption. Similar types of result have also been obtained elsewhere⁹.

We have also evaluated various thermodynamic parameters. Standard free energy, ΔG° calculated using the equation¹⁰, $\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln b$, was calculated to be $-6.99 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$. Apparent heat of reaction-enthalpy, ΔH° estimated using equation,

$$\ln \frac{k_2}{k_1} = \frac{\Delta H^\circ}{2.303 R} \left(\frac{1}{T_1} - \frac{1}{T_2} \right)$$

was calculated to be $-5.90 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$. Entropy, ΔS° of the system was calculated using equation, $\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T \Delta S^\circ$, was found to be $365 \text{ cal/g-mole/deg}$.

Solvent effect : The effect of solvents has been studied by adding various aliphatic alcohols (5%, v/v) to the glucose-alumina suspension. The results indicate that the amount of adsorbed glucose decreases with increasing number of carbon atoms in the alkyl chain of the solvent, thus obeying the following sequence of increasing depression, $\text{MeOH} < \text{EtOH} < i\text{-PrOH} < n\text{-BuOH}$. The results can be explained on the basis of the surface tensions of the alcohols : methanol 22.07, ethanol 21.97, isopropanol 20.93 and butanol 24.93 mN/m. It is clear that the surface tension gradually decreases with increasing number of carbon atoms. This will obviously lead to an increased tendency of alcohol molecules to be concentrated at the interface and thus their preferential adsorption results in decreased adsorption.

Conclusions : The adsorption of glucose onto alumina follows Langmuirian adsorption process and the adsorption is supposed to occur via the H-bonding between the aluminols of the alumina surface and glucose molecules. The adsorption is affected by the pH and a maximum adsorption is exhibited at near the isoelectric point of the alumina. On addition of anions to the alumina suspension, the adsorption increases with the increasing valency of the added anions, while it almost remains constant by cationic addition. The temperature also has an inverse effect on adsorption.

Experimental

Glucose (B.D.H.) was used without further purification. The final pH of the glucose solution was adjusted to 6.8. The adsorbent was the chromatographic grade alumina (B.D.H.) with specific surface area of $18.0 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ determined by BET measurements. Other chemicals used were of guaranteed reagent grade. Conductivity water was used throughout.

Method of adsorption : Adsorption experiments were carried out as described earlier¹¹. In brief, a glucose solution (25 ml) of known concentration containing alumina (200 mg) at fixed pH 6.8, was shaken for 2 h, sufficient time for attaining the adsorption equilibrium. The remaining amount of glucose in the supernatant solution was estimated colorimetrically¹². For kinetic measurements, several identical experiments were run simultaneously and progress of the reaction was recorded at definite time intervals as mentioned above. The amount of adsorbed glucose was then calculated.

It is worth mentioning here that at higher temperatures the alumina are known to catalyze partial degradation of glucose¹³. However, in the present study since the adsorption temperature is quite low ($25 \pm 0.2^\circ$), there is no possibility of such type of degradation.

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